

IMPROVING INTEGRATIVE MODULAR TEACHING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *This article describes the scientific-methodical foundations of formal, informal, informal teaching technologies through various forms of education (traditional, distance, online, dual) in the continuous professional development of primary school teachers. Also, examples of technologies for continuous professional development of primary school teachers and methodical instructions on their application are provided.*

Keywords: *continuous professional development of teachers, traditional, distance, online, dual education forms, formal, informal, informal teaching technologies.*

Introduction

In modern conditions, improving the mechanism of developing the intellectual potential of pedagogues in the system of public education, developing the infrastructure for its implementation has become the demand of the times. Today, multi-parameter concepts of intellectual development of public education workers based on humanitarianism are being promoted worldwide. Therefore, in practice, this process is a multi-component system that further improves the system of continuous professional development of teachers, expands innovative processes, diversifies educational services, introduces quality management, is based on professional needs, models individual activities, designs, ensures continuity and coherence. creates the need to implement approaches.

Literature review

The approaches developed by Y. V. Bondarevskaya, V. V. Serikov, N. K. Sergeev, V. A. Slastenin, S. A. Kotova, A. V. Petrovsky, I. S. Yakimanskaya and others in the modern concepts of person-oriented education help to determine the personal direction of education. They are the priority of personal-semantic development, the subjective experience of the learner, pedagogical support of his individuality, creation of conditions for self-action, personality development, the learner as a subject of education and life. based on the ideas of formation.

In the studies of M.V. Belov and D.A. Novikov, technology is interpreted as a system of conditions, criteria, forms, methods and tools for consistent achievement of the goal [2; page 8].

In the scientific researches of G. Ernazarova [9], controversial acmetechonology, developmental acmetechonology, training acmetechonology, game acmetechonologies and their application methods were noted as a means of ensuring the integration of pedagogical-psychological-acmeological tasks of education in science teaching.

In E.V. Lopanova's studies, the selection of educational technologies is based on such criteria as the content of teaching, individualization and differentiation of teaching, purposeful orientation taking into account its specific characteristics, readiness of the teacher to implement technology, profitability, material and technological security. 'focuses [7].

T.A. Dmitrenko developed the following criteria in his research on determining the most important features of career-oriented technologies in a higher pedagogical school: efficiency;

profitability; ergonomics / psycho-hygiene; creating a high motivation to study the subject; using the latest achievements of didactics; increase the informativeness of educational content; development of general educational skills; educational and methodological support that ensures high mental activity of students [3].

Research Methodology

As a result of studying the principles of technology selection, dissertation research on their requirements and the analysis of various scientific literature (V.I.Zagvyazinsky, M.M.Levina, E.S.Polat) and other points of view, we summarized the requirements for technologies for the professional development of teachers within the framework of our research: intensity of education; the possibility of modeling professional activity; ability to make decisions independently; high theoretical level of educational material; ensuring the quality of education; speed of data processing and guarantee of practical use; comprehensive solution of educational problems; personal direction; ensuring progress in cognitive development; connecting with the teacher's professional activity and taking into account his needs, individual professional development trajectory; increasing interest in professional activity and professional development; practical direction; the problematic nature of the educational material; having a developmental character; development of professional knowledge; compatibility of technologies with each other.

Modern science and practice has a variety of technologies that are sufficient to meet any needs of teachers. There are different bases for systematizing technology groups. Depending on the nature of the educational environment (or conditions), all known technological teaching methods can be divided into three groups [6]:

technological methods that can be used within the traditional classroom system (problematic education, developmental education, games, etc.);

technological methods that require organizational modernization of the work of an educational institution (concentrated education, collective method of teaching, etc.);

technological methods that require changing the content of education ("communication technologies", probability education, etc.).

In her research, O.A. Ivanova summarizes the technologies related to the organization of adult education in the following types [1]: modular teaching technology; modular-rating technology of education; modular credit technology of education; flexible educational system technology; full assimilation technology; multi-level educational technology; technology of individual educational trajectories; paracentric educational technology; control and correction technology; individual-team technology of teaching; team-individual technology of teaching and others.

Described by researchers for the andragogic model of education - individual education aimed at the self-development of adults in the direction of individual education and acquiring the skills to organize their own educational process The technology of lim trajectories is relevant.

Also, experts emphasize that the following six main groups of educational technologies can be distinguished depending on the leading (pillar) activity [4]:

explanatory and illustrative technologies (understanding, recognition);

reproductive technologies (performance);

problematic search technologies (research);

communication technologies (communication);

imitation and role-playing technologies (game);

reflective (reflective) technologies (reading, teaching).

In our opinion, the group of technologies for adult education proposed by Y.I. Mikhaylova, O.M. Chorosova, R.YE. Gerasimova, T.A. Makarenko in the continuous professional development of teachers should reflect the specific features of the organization of adult education and all known technological incorporates teaching methods.

Analysis and results

The problem of meeting the ever-growing needs of a person and developing one's personality is also very urgent, and adult education helps to improve one's personality and manifest one's identity. Self-development is the independent organization of practical actions on the basis of specific goals and well-thought-out tasks in order to improve professional experience, qualifications and skills. The main direction of professional development is personal development in the process of professional training, acquiring a profession, and performing professional activities. The process of professional formation of a person is unique individually, professional activity gives a person opportunities for self-awareness and self-development, the individual trajectory of a person's professional life is determined by normative and non-normative events, knowing the psychological characteristics of professional development is necessary for a person allows you to consciously design, build your professional biography, create your own history.

The high level of professional-pedagogical activity of student-teachers depends on the effective organization of training sessions in the system of continuous professional development. In order to ensure the effectiveness of training sessions, purposefully selected technologies and methods for organizing the training are of great importance.

Based on the above, we defined the technology of adult education as follows: adult education technology is a system of evidence-based actions of adult students and andragogic teachers, the implementation of which leads to the fulfillment of the needs of the state, society, teachers, and the achievement of educational goals in accordance with the needs of the labor market .

Adult education technology is a normative description of activities aimed at achieving the planned goals (initial, current and final status of the student-teacher, the process of achieving results, methods, tools and methods).

Adult education technology is implemented by adult students and andragogic teachers in the form of carrying out certain operations, technical actions and functions at each of the six stages of the educational process: diagnosis, planning, creating conditions, educational process implementation, evaluation and correction [5].

So, the following stand out as leading signs defining the essence of the concept of "technology" in adult education:

orientation: orientation to the activity of the listener-teacher, as opposed to orientation to science;

subjectivity: technology, unlike methodology, is not directly related to the content of any academic subject, it is basically universal in nature and can be applied to the content of various subjects;

processivity: designing the educational trajectory of the listener-teacher to the end;

reproducibility: a clear description of the program, procedures and stages of achieving goals that ensure the transferability of educational technologies;

cyclicity: the repeatability of the general structure of the student-teacher activity in each new educational cycle;

the presence of a reflexive component in the activity of the listener-teacher, which ensures the development of his competence and independence.

In this case, adult education is organized on the basis of the following scheme: "experience-reflection-knowledge-experience of application in changing situations". The purpose and result of such an organization of the educational process is determined by the developed competence of the specialist as an integral feature that represents the ability of a person to successfully perform certain activities.

In order to solve this problem, based on the study and generalization of the technologies of professional development of teachers from local and foreign experience, the use of teachers in formal, informal, informal education through various forms of education (traditional, distance, online, dual) combined technologies into three large conceptual groups: unified curriculum for teaching subjects in collective and small groups through the formal educational process, as well as directive-systematic through the curriculum created in accordance with the specific goals and objectives of education and training implementation technologies. Technologies in this group are used in the formal form of education and training of adults. Formal is an institutionalized (embodying specific rules and norms), purpose-oriented and planned education with the participation of state educational institutions and accredited non-governmental educational organizations recognized by the state.

Informal, self-directed and developing technologies based on teaching in pedagogic classrooms ("free lessons", "free creative works", "activities based on desire, need and motivation"). Informal - institutionalized by a person or organization that provides educational services (embodying certain rules and norms), directed and planned for a specific purpose, additional to formal education in training a person throughout his life and (or) its alternative. (informal) communicative and interactive technologies for obtaining information, based on practical and developing theories. These are didactic and methodical work in project-oriented groups, pair groups, team teaching (Team-Teaching), training in special rooms equipped with functional equipment, special training sessions, organizing free work according to the weekly schedule. are technologies related to making. Informal - goal-oriented, but not institutionalized (does not embody specific rules and norms), is less organized and structured than formal or informal education, and includes learning activities in the family, workplace, place of residence and everyday life can get

It is recommended to use these technologies in the process of professional development of teachers through traditional courses designed for classroom teaching.

Differential learning technologies.

Purpose: provides training taking into account the individual characteristics of the listener-teacher - the ability to learn and the ability to acquire knowledge.

The essence: this technology envisages the creation of a pedagogical environment that takes into account the activity of each learner in accordance with the scope of close development, and differential level education.

Mechanism: training based on the diagnosis of the dynamic characteristics of the person and the level of acquisition of general educational skills; choose depending on the areas of education and interests; organization of profile training options; activation of cognitive content and stimulation of cognitive activity of the listener-teacher; voluntary choice of learning material level (not less than state requirements and qualification requirements); organizing the independent work of the student-teacher; organizing the educational process in pairs, groups and teams; control

over learning material; targeted training of trainee-teachers according to specially developed content and methodology for the field of activity in the general secondary educational institution, for example, teachers teaching in 1st grades (as well as another grade) (teaching in separately organized groups regarding teaching methods and educational problems of subjects taught in 1st grades; quick training according to the personal education plan.

Technology for creative design of educational activities (Technology for creative design of educational activities). Design - artistic design of an object based on certain aesthetic characteristics.

Purpose: to activate the creative thinking of students-teachers; formation of problem-solving skills; develop the ability to consciously search for a solution to a problem.

The essence: creating a creative design of educational activities.

Mechanism: selection method - evaluating each of several alternative solutions, selecting the most appropriate one from among them depending on their importance; research method - possible defects and their causes are determined by indirect means; the method of diaries - the ideas born by each member of the group are written down in a certain period of time, and they are analyzed in the group and one average opinion is reached; 6-6 method - six members of the group write down their opinions and options on the solution of the problem in 6 minutes, then the group analyzes and selects the most important.

In this case, the following sequence of actions is performed:

Critical thinking of the state of the existing object (subject), formation of a problem situation, change of the problem situation based on specific creative tasks (initial data, conditions for determining the solution, necessary restrictions and means of implementation, clarity of the goal).

Conditions and principles of idea search, creative change and transformation (transformation into another form).

Development of an ideal model of development as a result of thought experiments.

Conducting and summarizing experimental work on the implementation of the model.

Analysis and interpretation and interpretation of results.

It is recommended to use these technologies in the process of continuous professional development of teachers through distance and online courses.

"Distant auditoriums" technology. Synchronous telecasting of training courses, lectures and seminars organized in a specific educational institution (specialized training centers) to the educational halls of educational institutions (general secondary educational institutions) located at a distance from it through telecommunication means. It is intended to be broadcast in the form of a show, videoconference and radio broadcast.

"Personal learning environment" (Personal learning environment) technologies.

Purpose: to create a self-directed and evolving environment of self-organized (print and electronic) tools, services, and resources for lifelong learning.

Essence: constant creation, updating and exchange of information.

Mechanism: perception; search; collect; collect; application; reflection; publishing; communication; cooperation; processing.

It is recommended to use this technology in the process of continuous professional development of teachers through courses designed for teaching in the form of dual education.

"Flipped class" technologies.

Purpose: to organize independent education of teachers-students and cooperative activities based on independently acquired knowledge.

The essence: to create an opportunity to establish feedback for continuous professional development.

Mechanism: determining the topic and its content; creation of educational and methodological support; preparation of instructions for working with materials; establishing contact with students; practical training.

Conclusion/Recommendations

If the teacher as a person has internal adaptation and ways of thinking to create news, he will easily express his attitude to all changes, evaluate them correctly, manage them and implement them in his professional field. According to the results of the research conducted in this regard, the implementation of the above tasks is determined by the preparation of pedagogical personnel for innovative activities in the system of continuous professional development of teachers. In this process, organizing and conducting practical trainings that fully cover the teacher's pedagogical capabilities, can demonstrate his professional potential, and take into account his psychological and individual capabilities, is of special importance. In this case, it is appropriate to pay attention to practical training of student-teachers based on the theoretical information they have acquired in the process of professional development.

Thus, in the conditions of market relations, the need to be resistant to strong competition in the labor market encourages each specialist to develop professional competence and qualities specific to him.

As can be seen from the above opinions and considerations, the differential approach to determining the professional needs of public education workers and improving their qualifications is considered an urgent problem. Solving such problems, in turn, requires the creation of an effective system of continuous professional development of teachers. The conclusion is that pedagogues should independently improve their knowledge outside the audience and acquire the necessary knowledge of science. It is important to acquire pedagogical skills that ensure the effectiveness of the teaching process through independent education, the formation of professional thinking that means political and humanitarian knowledge, the system of pedagogical knowledge and teaching technologies in the field of specialization.

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